

LIVING ABROAD

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Abstract. *With the proliferation of international exchange programs and globalization, living abroad has been increasingly common for individuals for many years over the globe. This type of lifestyle can not only create a high-quality living standards, but also cause a slippery slope of challenges such as financial strain, loneliness, homesickness, language barriers.*

Key words: *international exchange programs, gaining excellence, well paying job opportunity, practical and emotional (mental) problems.*

ПРОЖИВАЮЩИЙ ЗА ГРАНИЦЕЙ, НЕРЕЗИДЕНТ

Аннотация. *С появлением программ международного обмена и глобализацией жизнь за границей на протяжении многих лет становится все более распространенной для людей по всему миру. Такой образ жизни может не только создать качественный уровень жизни, но и стать причиной возникновения таких проблем, как финансовое напряжение, одиночество, тоска по дому, языковые барьеры.*

Ключевые слова: *международные программы обмена, повышение квалификации, возможность хорошо оплачиваемой работы, практические и эмоциональные (психические) проблемы.*

From the social standpoint, a person who is living in a foreign country can experience detrimental issues such as a difficult usage of transport, grocery shopping due to a lack of host country's language proficiency. Moreover, they can face some financial issues, for example, a lack of income. They struggle with to find high-salary job opportunity.

From an academic point of view, they can not engage with university subjects, extracurricular activities in academic settings. Apart from this, they find it difficult to make friends in university area, as overseas students can not communicate with and build strong contact local residents in their mother tongue as though local inhabitants. Moreover, living abroad and overwhelming homework loads due to gaining excellence over young groups can pose a heavy burden on their shoulders as well as the pressure of low self-esteem from elementary school ages.

High expectations can cause a slippery slope of debilitating feelings and health problems like chronic sleep deprivation, eye strain, poor posture. With the advent of standardized testing system parents tend to be academically excel in school subjects and extra-curricular activities. In this way, children feel compelled themselves to score highly in school subjects. All of those pressure can manifest in various ways, such as anxiety, stress, physical health issues.

A sense of perpetual pressure can interfere with a child's social and mental development. Parents, policymakers should recognize the toll that academic stress is taking on young learners and implement measures. To alleviate this burden government can make many laws. As a consequence of fierce rivalry youngs are experiencing social isolation and estrangement. All of which cause addiction to social media, mental and emotional health challenges, bullying. Thus, they try to find a sense of luckiness, to be considered valuable and successful from materialistic possessions by presenting a curated and idealized version of themselves on the social media sites.

Parents, co-parents, government should provide support and guidance to navigate these challenges. Making it crucial for policymakers to enhance young's holistic development.

From an emotional standpoint, all people struggle with mental and practical problems homesickness, loneliness, debilitating feelings like low-self estimation, depression, stress when they begin their life as a newcomer. Furthermore, they can face more problems based on financial strain, especially students and workers find it difficult to meet their family with food due to high-living standarts in overseas countries. At some point in life, with the impact of other people, the ordinary newcomers can be cheaten by them. As a consequence, crime rates become higher in those countries.

In addition to criminal behavior, law enforcement agency can reduce crime rates by implementing a zero-tolerance approach, no matter how minor. Stringent punishmen, lengthy prison sentences serve as an effective deterrant for potential offenders. Furthermore, government, people can not only reduce stigmatization, prejudice against ex-offenders, but also help for promoting rehabilitation, reintegration programs.

Apart from this, offering high-quality education can be the best solution. Moreover, by conducting targeted enforcemenet like identification and addressing crime hotspots, installing surveillance cameras, holding criminals accountable for their wrongdoings. By ensuring swift consequences for criminal behavior instill a sense of fear into the hearts of potential and existing law-breakers. In addition to law enforcement measures, by addressing the root causes of crime policymakers can prevent crime.

The availability of stable and well-paying jobs, cutting taxes on business allow to hire more works, providing opportunities for entrepreneurship offer vocational programs. As job option increase, so does salary. In terms of reducing crime rates, by successfully reintegrating back into society recidivism rates can be lowered. Mental health treatment, substance abuse treatment, vocational training, assistance with finding decent housing and employment, underlying causes of criminal behavior can be addressed.

Providing a path towards rehabilitation ex-criminals become productive and low-abiding members of society, all of which can help reducing the likelihood of reoffending and ensuring optimal community safety. By offering accessible and comprehensive education programs quality education system can be achieved. The advent of making well-informed, rational decision, avoiding antisocial behavior make positive contribution to society as well as empowering future generation.

Raising public awareness about crime and its impact on communities reduce the risk of engaging in criminal acts. In spite of those, promoting community involvement, fostering a sense of collective responsibility can more likely to take an active role in combating crime. Community outreach, neighbourhood watch initiatives, fostering collaboration with law enforcement promote a culture of vigilance and support.

As a general, living abroad has many advantages as wll as disadvantages. Benefits can be used for high quality education system in developed countries by international students as well as well paying job opportunities in those areas.

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